

INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS FOR BUILDING INFORMATION MODELLING (BIM)

The Project **Urban PERISCOPE INTEGRATED/0918/0034** is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Innovation Foundation.

Abstract

The purpose of the Exchange Information Requirements document is to provide support and to serve as a requirements guide for the design and production of the necessary semantically enriched datasets of the pilot buildings, which were selected by the project Expert Group (10 buildings in the Old Strovolos core district, Nicosia, and 9 buildings in the Cami Cedid and Arnaut districts, and city centre of Limassol) to function as testbeds for the development of the UP Platform. These datasets of multi-disciplinary representations of the pilot buildings will be created as central models to be hosted on an open-source, online platform, which will provide access to these datasets, previously generated in T4.3 (WP4), through a BIM viewer. The objective of this process is data integration and flow optimization, creating a hierarchy of the information (i.e., metadata linked with 3D assets), according to the Heritage BIM (HBIM) goals. The amount of data available will be filtered according to the parameters that are useful for management and system maintenance. Throughout the various phases of this process, the Exchange Information Requirements document provides an operational framework to guide the modellers through the technical modalities of BIM processes. These phases are described in the BIM Execution Plan to ensure consistency and coherence in the use of the BIM software.

This guideline document is based on a standard Exchange Information Requirements (EIR) Template based on ISO 19650-1, which is required for service agreements or contracts following the Construction Industry Council (CIC) BIM Standards and methodology.

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This document is a guidance template for an Employer’s Information Requirements (EIR) and should be used to draft a particular EIR for each case study. Throughout this document, guidance has been included as red panels like this and will need to be deleted prior to issue.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Document purpose

This document provides the Exchange Information Requirements (*EIR*) for the development of a virtual model *[to add the specific building to be modelled]* using the Heritage Building Information Modelling (HBIM) process, in the context of the RIF project Urban PERISCOPE (UP), as described in WP7. HBIM here refers to BIM method enriched by historical information and adapted to the particularities and purpose of the conservation and preservation of heritage buildings, including construction phasing, conservation state analysis, material provenance, historical and cultural information. The purpose of the Exchange Information Requirements is to outline how to develop and implement requirements for the application of HBIM and explain how to include these requirements regarding the phase of the project. Also, this document outlines the followings, to support collaborative processes and procedures the information required during different phases of the project:

- Responsibilities
- Requirements and processes
- Standards
- Best practices
- Methods and protocols
- Relevant processes
- Supporting software requirements
- Deliverables

In line with the definition of ISO 19650, the EIR is a “*tender document setting out the information to be delivered, and the standards and processes to be adopted by the Consultant as part of the project delivery process*”. The EIR outlines the UP strategic approach and it specifies the management, technical, commercial and project information and deliverables required for the project in a way that is specific, measurable, achievable and realistic. All data producers and professionals involved in UP must adhere to and follow the EIR.

UP EIR shall accompany the tender documents. Making this information available at tender enables consultants to make informed decisions in the planning, design and delivery of the digital asset, in readiness for optimal use in the operational phase.

The consultant is to include a *BIM Execution Plan (BEP)* in the proposal, in which it must detail how it proposes to meet the Employer’s (Municipality, building owner) requirements. The completed EIR and subsequent BEP are key documents used to assess the contents and quality of the tender response. Throughout this EIR, specific responses are sought from the consultant through the BEP.

1.2 Scope

This Guide establishes recommendations that can be continually shared and agreed upon by the stakeholders and the UP project BIM team. The scope of this guide is to support the implementation of HBIM by the UP team and data producers.

1.3 General Project Information

This tender concerns the development of an HBIM model of *[to add the specific building to be modelled]* within the UP project. The UP project aims to enhance the capacity of public local administrations and local stakeholders to monitor, design, and realize rehabilitation interventions on existing heritage buildings through a multidisciplinary and integrated ICT tool (BIM and performance-based design approach). The testing of this emerging technology on built heritage will be performed to demonstrate its scalability to the entire building stock of historic clusters in Cypriot cities.

The HBIM model should integrate previously collected information on the building, including geometric and diagnostic data collected within this survey/tender. Moreover, the HBIM model will be used as a basis to develop and test the capacity of the proposed-UP platform to integrate all relevant multidisciplinary metadata that are necessary to be used in renovation operations and the implementation of design scenarios.

1.4 Building information

[to add specific information on the building subject to the EIR]

1.5 Glossary

Unless the context otherwise requires, the following words and phrases shall have the following meanings:

AEG

Architecture, Engineering and Construction.

Asset

Item, thing, or entity that has potential or actual value to an organization.

BEP

BIM Execution Plan. A plan that explains how the information management aspects of the appointment will be carried out by the delivery team.

BIM

Building Information Model / Modelling. Use of a shared digital representation of a built asset to facilitate construction, operation design, and processes to form a reliable basis for decisions.

HBIM

Heritage Building Information modeling (HBIM) can be defined as a semantic-aware database of historical buildings, in which the geometric model is connected to descriptive multi-source information. It consists of a useful tool in the historical documentation (e.g., phasing) and conservation (e.g., state analysis) of built structures.

Scan to BIM

The capture of the space, and turning it into a digital model that can be used for planning, monitoring or managing the built environment and communicating and sharing project information with stakeholders.

BS

Building Smart, (International Industry body)

BOQ

Bill of quantities

CDE

Common Data Environments

CIM

City Information Modelling

CoBie

Construction Operations Building Information Exchange. The international standard for information exchange about construction, data is focused from a BIM methodology point of view.

DES

Data Exchange Schemas

Digital Twin

A digital twin is a virtual parametric model designed to accurately represent a physical object.

IFC

Industry Foundation Class (Digital file format)

ISO

International Organization for Standardization

LCA

Life Cycle Analysis

LOD

Level of Development. It defines the level of Information contained in a BIM model.

MEP

Mechanical, Electrical and Plumbing

MVD

Model View Definition

Point Cloud

The result of a data collection of a building or object by a laser scanner or photogrammetry, consisting of a set of points in the space that reflect its surface.

NDT

Non-Destructive Techniques

Space

A space is defined as a building volume enclosed by ceilings, floors, walls, or another space's boundary. Space has a plethora of properties assigned to it to describe its energy resources, such as loads from people, lighting, and equipment.

MF

Model federation Creation of a composite information model from separate models. An assembly of distinct models to create a single, complete building information model of an asset.

OmniClass

The OmniClass Construction Classification System, also known as OmniClass™ or OCCS, is a classification system used for the organising and retrieving of information for the construction industry. For more information, see <https://www.csiresources.org/standards/omniclass>.

Model - Digital representation of part of the physical and/or functional characteristics of the Project.

Project - means the project to which the EIR relates.

Standards

Standards are documents created to establish minimum levels of quality or achievement that are acceptable using BIM. More details are submitted in Chapter §11. *HBIM-definitions - Details and Standards* and 12. *Standards on Technical specifications for the geometric survey and general conservation state visual analysis tender*.

BIM Maturity

3.1 BIM

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a method that defines all the collaborative processes that create, distribute and re-use a structured and ordered database of the work (to be) produced based on open standards of the Industry, which are used to produce graphical representation documents and data spreadsheets throughout a project's lifecycle. Its main objective is to enable the different actors of a project, such as architects, engineers, contractors, maintainers, promoters, concessionaires and licensors, to exchange and share information, in a transparent, efficient and collaborative way through a common data format, e.g., IFC (Information For Construction) and/or native software file formats (such as Autodesk®'s Revit® RVT, etc.), revolutionizing the drafting practice based on Computer-Aided Design (CAD).

BIM's technical and operational richness comes from its shared use by the actors of the project.

The requirements that constitute the two fundamental uses of BIM for a successful approach are:

1. the level of maturity of BIM to be applied (at least the collaborative level 2 - see §12.3 *BIM Levels, Technical specifications for the geometric survey and general conservation state visual analysis tender*).
2. and the '3D native BIM objects modelling' (by using assets classification hierarchy method according to systems engineering).

3.2 '3D Modelling' and 'BIM' differences

A 3D model can be produced from any 3D modelling software (BIM or not) to represent the geometry in support of the visualisation of built structures, incl. creating photorealistic renderings with light simulation. Importing the 3D model into BIM software retains all the geometry. The 3D model is thus used with the sole purpose of visualizing the building - hence the EIR does not apply to it.

A BIM model can be a multidimensional model (3D, 4D [time] and 5D [cost]) in which an unlimited amount of information is entered on each constituent object/part of the building as a collection of attributes.

A BIM model is scalable not only in terms of scope, completeness and complexity but also in terms of the extent of its applications and uses during all phases of a project's life cycle, from design to maintenance. BIM modelling can be defined as the 3D modelling of structures using interoperable** and object-oriented CAD systems* capable of representing the physical properties and non-graphic attributes of a built structure as a virtual model tied to a database.

BIM modelling allows:

- The production of 2D deliverables from BIM models
- The production of the deliverable project BIM models

* Object-oriented CAD systems replaced 2D symbols with structural elements or objects from a preconfigured library, capable of representing the characteristics of common structural elements. These structural elements can be displayed in multiple views, and non-graphic attributes can be assigned to them, thus enabling such elements or objects to become “intelligent.” This combination of parametric 3D geometry with assigned rules and dimensions allows the representation of complex geometric and functional relationships between structural elements. Parametric objects are defined as parameters with relationships to other objects, allowing such objects to automatically re-build themselves based on the rules embedded in them (for example, if a window is defined as being wholly within a wall, and if the wall is moved by the designer, the window automatically moves in space following with the wall).

** Interoperability means interaction between different software in data flow/conversion. The interoperability between different software is their ability to communicate by importing and exporting graphical and non-graphical readable data. The fact that they are object-oriented is usually a prerequisite for this possibility. Open interoperability is defined as open interoperability when the exchange format is open, such as the IFC standard.

The distinction between a 3D model and a BIM Digital Model lies in the level of information carried by the BIM Model.

3D models (without BIM Properties) are for example:

- The environmental parameters of a project.
- The 3D Digital Terrain Model (topographic representation of the site) embodying the plot and its immediate surroundings concerned by the project.
- Generic environments (.MNT 3D, Bâti 3D, etc.).

3.3 BIM Levels

According to the international standard ISO 19650, there are three main BIM levels:

Figure 1 – BIM maturity levels @BS1192-2

For more details and an extensive analysis please see on §12.3 BIM Levels, *Technical specifications for the geometric survey and general conservation state visual analysis tender*.

3.4 Level of Information Need

The Level of Information Need defines the level of maturity required for a particular information deliverable at a particular plan of work stage. It provides a framework that defines the extent and granularity of information and helps to prevent the delivery of too much information.

3.5 BIM Uses

BIM usage is an explanation of processes that comprise BIM practices and fulfil the BIM goals of a project. The identification of BIM Use/Goals defines the project and team values. The project BIM goals should lead to the choice of BIM Uses and additional BIM requirements.

Uses	Description
Existing Conditions modelling	Geometric survey with aerial and terrestrial documentation techniques – The integration of state-of-the-art techniques (topographic survey, terrestrial laser scanners, photogrammetry) in the survey phase will supply an accurate and critical representation of the site and surrounding buildings and will provide the basis for geometric modelling of the HBIM model based on the existing construction (see Technical specifications for the geometric survey and general conservation state visual analysis tender).
Design authoring	A process in which the UP-BIM project team will develop the 3D model of the existing conditions (all or only a portion depending on the project needs) of the selected buildings.
Management of the knowledge documentation on the historical building	This task involves data optimization, the creation of an hierarchy of the information (i.e., metadata linked with 3D assets), according to the BIM model goals. The amount of data available will be filtered according to the parameters useful for management and system maintenance.
UP BIM platform	The HBIM models will be created as central models to be hosted on online UP BIM platform.
Cost analysis	A systematic approach to estimating the strengths and weaknesses of alternatives used to determine options which provide the best approach to achieving benefits while preserving savings.
General conservation state (materials and structure survey) & LCA / Environmental Assessment	The visual observation, interpretation and detection, non-destructive structural analysis and mapping of the various spatial and structural alteration and decay patterns found on the exposed surfaces and macroscopic elements of criticality affecting the structure of the building will be reported on the HBIM model to inform the programming of intervention and maintenance plan. The environmental impact of the proposed tool will be quantified through the implementation of life cycle assessment (LCA) studies for the pilot buildings.
Sustainability analysis	This process will occur during all stages of a building’s life, including planning, design and operation. Applying sustainability features to the HBIM model is used to calculate the environmental impact of a new construction project or an existing building.
Life cycle costing	Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is the consideration of all ‘relevant’ costs and revenues associated with the acquisition and ownership of a building asset. LCC has several relevant applications, these include project appraisal; facilities management; procurement and tendering and as a means to evaluate sustainable construction.
Virtual Reality Simulation	The HBIM model of a building is accessed through an immersive environment (VR) where users experience simulated site, objects and conditions of the heritage building.

The descriptions were developed to provide a brief overview for UP project team and project team members who may not be familiar with the HBIM use and to provide additional information that the

project team may find valuable. Each description includes an overview of the BIM Use and potential benefits.

The HBIM uses proposed are recommendation; it is advised to appropriate, add and draft them according to the specificities of each project.

BIM Project Organization

4.1 Project phases

The project phases for the entire life cycle of a built structure are identified below:

Figure 2 –BIM Cyclic diagram as adopted by the UP team base on BIM-Definition des National Building Information Model Standard Project Committee (NBIM)

4.2 Design phases

The purpose of this section is to define the model uses of the HBIM model to be developed, as listed below:

Goals	Description
HBIM modelling (WP7 Task 7. 1)	The 3D representations of the pilot buildings selected (located in the Old Strovolos core district, Nicosia, and in the Cami Cedid and Arnaut districts, Limassol) to function as testbeds for the development of the UP platform will produced, based on <i>Technical specifications for the geometric survey and general conservation state visual analysis tender</i> .

User testing (WP7 Task 7. 2)	The BIM model will perform as a database server and a workspace for consultation with the stakeholders who do not operate in 3D. This step of the process involves the first evaluation of the condition of each building to be studied, the creation of the pre-contractual Historical BIM Execution Plan (HBEP) and the potential values of the building in terms of cultural dissemination.
Data integration (WP7 Task 7. 3)	The BIM modelling process includes the creation of BIM materials and libraries of construction details, as well as BIM families with specific architectural and demorative elements. The generated BIM model (and linked building dataset) will be administered through the UP platform, which will be easily customizable to address its end-users' needs (see Task 9.3).
Data curation for BPS purposes (WP7 Task 7. 4)	In this task, the building datasets will be checked for their compatibility and readiness to be used for Building Performance Simulation operations for retrofit purposes, in the future – a capacity to be offered to the users of the UP platform due to the strategic decision of the UP to implement and respect the relevant international standards, file formats and good practices that allow interoperability of the generated data. After the building model is evaluated and approved by the relevant experts/stakeholders, the 'as-built' BIM model is stored, published and uploaded/integrated to the UP platform.

The information to be integrated in/linked with the BIM model, provided by the Employer, should be defined in further detail according to the purpose of the operation. Here, the implementation of BIM method in the various project design phases regards specifically the Level of Geometrical Information and Level of Detail of the assets.

4.3 BIM Project Process

A BIM project Process is presented below:

Figure 3– Project BIM Process

4.4 Roles and responsibilities

The purpose of this section is to stipulate the allocation of roles and responsibilities associated with the management of the model and project information.

The Consultant indicates the Project Team Members carrying the following roles, indicating their capability and experience to fulfil the requirements of the roles. The same person can fulfil different roles:

Figure 1 – Project Team Organization Chat.

4.5 Project Documents – BIM Execution Plan

The *BIM Project Execution Plan* is the central document for BIM implementation. This plan should be authored by the BIM Manager and validated by the Project manager. It should mainly describe BIM processes that should be developed from and for the Project BIM Team.

The Project Execution Planning Procedure is presented below by the USA National BIM Guide for Owners:

Figure 4– BIM Project Execution Planning Procedure

The final product of the execution planning process is a document, the *BIM Project Execution Plan (BEP)*. The BEP should contain all content necessary to document the process of implementing BIM on a project. To maximize the effectiveness of BIM, the BEP should be designed in the early stages of a project and focus on the decisions required to define the scope of BIM implementation on the project. The BEP should be considered a living document that evolves throughout the duration of the project.

The initial version BEP should be developed and refined by the *BIM Project Manager* to document the collaborative process of how BIM will be executed throughout the project's life cycle.

The content of a BEP should describe (minimum requirements): Project Information, Project Goals and BIM Uses, Project BIM Management, BIM collaboration process, Data management and workflows, BIM Model Requirements, regarding the organization, and File structure, BIM Model Naming convention, BIM Model Validation and review, QA/QC control procedure, BIM deliverables.

4.6 Data sharing and collaboration

[UP project will have a common CDE for all the case studies;]

The Employer and Consultant should establish an agreed protocol for coordinating and sharing models, including how they will be controlled for quality and for ensuring the security of information. Information may flow both ways.

The Employer will provide a Common Data Environment (CDE) complying with ISO 19650 and ISO 27001, to be used by the Consultant for the management or sharing of data. The Employer will further indicate the access and sharing procedures to be followed by the Consultant. This must facilitate collaboration and information sharing between members of the project team. Common BIM standards covering detailed processes within each organisation must be established and agreed in advance.

The Consultant shall, post-contract award, liaise with the Employer to confirm details of personnel and their respective access permissions for the setup and use of the CDE by the security classifications/standards above.

4.7 Naming Convention

For the file naming convention, the Employer will provide a naming specification, to be used for all document types uploaded to a CDE, in line with IEC 82045-1 and BS 1192:2007(A2) 2016.

All the naming convention is described in detail in [Name Convention Document](#).

4.8 Model Quality Control

The Consultant Pre-contract BEP shall outline the processes to address model quality control and clash detection.

4.9 Modelling strategy

The Consultant shall define in the [BIM Project Execution Plan \(BEP\)](#) the main modelling strategy to fulfil the given model uses, to be further developed with the Employer, when awarded.

The modelling process will be based on the [UP Playbook](#) – Revit and on the [BIM Project Execution Plan \(BEP\)](#), provided.

The modelling process shall be based on geometric and technical information (geometric survey, drawings, etc.) provided by the Employer. Based on the provided information, the model shall represent the construction system and material characteristics of the building, including its service systems (vertical and horizontal structural system, material, etc.) and as accurately as possible within the Level of Information Need. The walls, roofs and floors shall be modelled with their stratigraphy (known or assumed by site observation). Architectural decorative elements can have a simplified representation, as long as their constructive system is detailed.

If a terrestrial laser scanner 3D documentation survey is to be provided by means of a 3D point cloud, then the Employer should further indicate the required tolerance from the 3D point cloud, depending on the building complexity. The Consultant shall take advantage of the parametric tools of BIM software (e.

g., system families) as much as possible, avoiding non-parametric representations, such as mesh modelling. The correct representation of the building technical, constructive and environmental features is paramount, even when leading to simplification of uneven features, which is typical in historical buildings. If the project is awarded, then the Consultant shall develop a simplification strategy for the building representation (e.g., assuming planarity of walls) together with the Employer.

The Consultant shall incorporate historical and diagnostic information (materials and structure survey, energy analyses, etc.) provided by the Employer in the model. If the information cannot be directly integrated into the BIM elements, it should be linked using reports, sheets, drawings, etc. When awarded, the Consultant shall respect and apply the UP data integration strategy, or negotiate alternations with the Employer.

To support Life Cycle Assessment and Environmental Assessment, the Consultant must integrate into the model the energy information provided by the LCA Manager (e.g., transmittance values for walls and windows, occupancy data, etc.). Occupancy and uses profiles for each room and/or thermal zones, if not included in the model, shall be linked as external files (reports, sheets, etc.). More details are described on the *NDT procedure* document.

Regarding object insertion and constraints, all objects (walls, roofs, ceilings, floors, HVAC systems, structures, windows, etc.) must be constrained to the corresponding lower and upper level.

All design preparation is described in detail in the Drawing Manual Guide - Revit. Further information regarding BIM Model Requirements are developed in the Drawing office Manual-Revit and the BIM Execution Plan.

TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS

5.1 Hardware infrastructure

Data processing

UP project team is required to define the hardware that supports the BIM software tools required and the size/nature of the project. The Consultant shall describe in the BEP the characteristics of each infrastructure item (computer) that will be used for the project, following the table below:

Infrastructure item	Description
Operating system	
Processor	
Memory	
Monitor	
Graphic	
Storage	

The Consultant shall describe in the BEP the Internet connection type and speed involved in the project.

5.2 Software infrastructure

At the beginning of the design phase of the project, the software tools used and their version must be defined. The official version of the software to be used in the project will be mentioned in the BEP. Any update or change of the version is to be agreed and validated by the Project Manager and BIM Manager and communicated to any involved party.

It is essential that the native BIM file formats delivered can be openly shared, and software platform systems can export to IFC (Industry Foundation Classes - latest version) for information extraction, verification, archive and free model viewing purposes.

Activity	Software	Version	Open format compatibility
3D Models			
2D Drawings			
Visualisations			
Reporting			
Schedules			
Bills of Quantities			

Note:

- In REVIT, the Central model of the project should mention the exact version of REVIT.
- The rollback to the previous version of REVIT is not applicable.
- Attention is required for the rollback to a version of other software like Rhino, Maya, etc.
- In case of the use of Add-in in REVIT a list of add-ins shall be created and updated, including the location of the setup file of the add-in.

5.3 Data exchange formats

The Employer requires information to be delivered about file formats, as listed below:

Software formats	
Method of Data Exchange	CDE
3D Graphical Data Exchange	IFC (latest version), native (all required)
Format of 2D Graphical Data Exchange	PDF
Documentation	*e57, *rcp

5.4 Common coordinates system

The coordinate system will be provided by the Employer.

Other coordination standards to be defined in the Pre-contract BEP are as follows:

- Units to be used for length [m/cm/mm];
- Units to be used for the area [m²/cm²/mm²];
- Units to be used for volume [m³/cm³/mm³].

5.6 BIM experience and competence

The Consultant shall provide in the BEP details of projects executed within a BIM-enabled environment in the table below. (Please provide a maximum of five suitable examples).

N.	Year	Project name	Project value	Type of service	Model uses and objectives

COMMERCIAL REQUIREMENTS

6.1 Deliverables

The Employer's project-specific Data Drops and Project Deliverables are listed below. The Consultant shall outline within the *BEP* how she will meet these requirements.

6.2 BIM tender assessment

[The Employer can amend this section and associated weighting table to suit the specific project needs]

The project tender assessment by the Employer will include assessing:

- The Consultant's response to the EIR in the *BEP*;
- The information in the Consultant BIM assessment form.

The following evaluation weights will be used by the client in assessing the tender response and BIM capabilities:

Score	Response	Match to the requirements
0	No response	No answer or inappropriate
1	Unacceptable	Significant concerns regarding the response/solution

2	Poor	Some reservations about the response/solution – may require further clarification before award
3	Fair	Meets the expected requirements
4	Good	Good response/solution which comprehensibly meets the requirements with an increased probability of meeting the desired outcome

Intellectual property rights

During all design phases, every HBIM model of a building remains the **exclusive** property of the respective UP stakeholder depending on its ownership, as described in the documentation of the UP platform:

- Private properties' datasets belong to the property owner(s), and can be accessed by authorities.
- Pilot buildings that are owned by the authorities (e.g., Municipality) belong to the owner and the Project partnership, and are freely accessible to the public for demonstration purposes.